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PROGRESSIVELY IMPLEMENTING HUMAN RIGHTS AND GENDER EQUALITY IN EVALUATION

Challenges and next steps

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Abstract

This discussion paper is dedicated to the question of how human rights and gender equality can be systematically integrated into the evaluation practice of development cooperation. Based on the observation that, despite far-reaching frameworks and political guidelines, the de-facto implementation of human rights-based approaches in evaluations remains incomplete. The aim of the paper is therefore to promote a conceptual understanding of human rights-based evaluation and to provide practical guidelines for its implementation. The introduction of the Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale (HRIIS) and its application to human rights principles are at the focus of the paper. The HRIIS identifies three levels of intensity in how human rights principles are integrated: sensitive, responsive, and transformative. By introducing the HRIIS, attention is paid to the idea that evaluations should not be understood exclusively as “human rights-based” or “non-human rights-based” but can be designed gradually – or progressively - along a continuum. The paper emphasises that the progressive implementation of human rights-based evaluations promotes both high-quality evaluations and more equitable evaluation practices. The discussion paper aims to contribute to and encourage the further development of professional and human rights-based evaluation practice and to invite critical reflection within the evaluation community.

Keywords: human rights-based evaluation, human rights, gender equality, human rights principles, participation, empowerment, non-discrimination, equality of opportunities, accountability, transparency, Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale, progressive realisation

Zusammenfassung

Dieses Diskussionspapier widmet sich der Frage, wie Menschenrechte und Geschlechtergerechtigkeit systematisch in die Evaluierungspraxis der Entwicklungszusammenarbeit integriert werden können. Ausgangspunkt ist die Feststellung, dass trotz weitreichender methodischer Grundlagen und politischer Leitlinien die tatsächliche Umsetzung menschenrechtsbasierter Ansätze in Evaluierungen bislang lückenhaft bleibt. Ziel des Papiers ist es daher, ein konzeptionelles Verständnis menschenrechtsbasierter Evaluation zu fördern und praxisnahe Orientierungen für deren Umsetzung bereitzustellen. Im Zentrum steht die Einführung der *Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale* (HRIIS) und ihre Anwendung auf menschenrechtliche Prinzipien. Die HRIIS unterscheidet drei Intensitätsstufen hinsichtlich der Stärke der Integration menschenrechtlicher Prinzipien: menschenrechtssensitiv, -responsiv und -transformativ. Mit der Einführung der HRIIS wird der Idee Rechnung getragen, dass Evaluierungen nicht ausschließlich als „menschenrechtsbasiert“ oder „nicht menschenrechtsbasiert“ zu verstehen sind, sondern entlang eines Kontinuums graduell – oder schrittweise – gestaltet werden können. Das Papier betont, dass die schrittweise Umsetzung menschenrechtsbasierter Evaluierungen sowohl qualitativ hochwertige Evaluierungen fördert als auch gerechtere evaluativere Praktiken. Mit dem Discussion Paper soll zur Weiterentwicklung professioneller und menschenrechtsbasierter Evaluierungspraxis beitragen und angeregt und zur kritischen Reflexion innerhalb der Evaluierungsgemeinschaft eingeladen werden.

Schlüsselbegriffe: Menschenrechtsbasierte Evaluierung, Menschenrechte, Gleichberechtigung der Geschlechter, Menschenrechtliche Prinzipien, Partizipation, Empowerment, Nichtsdiskriminierung, Chancengleichheit, Rechenschaft, Transparenz, Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale, progressive realisation.

CONTENTS

1.	Introduction	1
1.1	Background	1
1.2	Objective and scope of the discussion paper	2
2.	Core Concepts.....	4
2.1	Human rights and gender equality: what do we really mean?	4
2.2	What is the human rights-based approach to development?	4
2.3	How can we assess the gender equality and human rights orientation of development programmes?.....	5
2.4	What are the key human rights principles and standards?.....	8
2.5	Why is the dynamic of human rights and the HRBA to development important?.....	11
3.	Progressively implementing human rights and gender equality in evaluation practice	13
3.1	How to find the suitable level of intensity for a human rights-based evaluation?	13
3.2	What are the key aspects in the design of human rights-based evaluations?.....	17
3.3	How to set the stage in the evaluation process?	19
3.4	How can human rights principles gradually be implemented in the evaluation process?	21
3.4.1	Participation and empowerment	21
3.4.2	Non-discrimination and equality of opportunities	25
3.4.3	Accountability and transparency.....	27
3.5	How are human rights principles and professional evaluation standards linked?	30
4.	Summary and conclusions	33
5.	References	35

Figures

Figure 1	Comparison of gender and human right scales.....	7
Figure 2	Interpretation of the OECD DAC evaluation criteria (adapted from OECD (2023)).....	14
Figure 3	UNEG guidance on human rights and gender equality (HR and GE) in the evaluation process (adapted from UNEG, 2014, Chapters 4-7).....	15
Figure 4	The Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale.....	16
Figure 5	Types of participation of rights-holders in the evaluation process	22
Figure 6	Progressively implementing human rights principles in evaluations	34

Tables

Table 1	AAAQ framework and health rights	11
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Boxes

Box 1	The UN Common Understanding on a HRBA to Development Cooperation	5
Box 2	Examples of guiding evaluation questions incorporating human rights principles	18
Box 3	Human rights and gender equality in theories of change	19
Box 4	Types of duty-bearers and rights-holders in evaluations of development cooperation	20
Box 5	Participation of rights-holders in evaluation teams	23
Box 6	Participation of rights-holders in reference groups	24
Box 7	UNICEF study on cost-effectiveness of health and nutrition interventions	27
Box 8	Applying human rights impact assessment tools in evaluations	29
Box 9	Operationalising the principle of progressive realisation by applying the AAAQ criteria	29
Box 10	Evaluations and the right to remedies and redress	30

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

AAAQ	Availability, Accessibility, Acceptability, Quality
AI	Amnesty International
BMZ	Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development)
CEDAW	Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women
CRC	Convention on the Rights of the Child
DAC	Development Assistance Committee
DeGEval	Gesellschaft für Evaluation
DEval	Deutsches Evaluierungsinstitut der Entwicklungszusammenarbeit (German Institute for Development Evaluation)
EDA	Eidgenössisches Departement für auswärtige Angelegenheiten (Swiss Federal Department of Foreign Affairs, FDFA)
HRBA	Human Rights-based Approach
HRIA	Human Rights Impact Assessment
HRIIS	Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale
LNOB	Leave No One Behind
MFAD	Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Denmark
MFAF	Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NORAD	Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation
OHCHR	Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights
SIDA	Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency
ToC	Theory of Change
UN	United Nations
UNEG	United Nations Evaluation Group
UNFPA	United Nations Population Fund
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
WWF	World Wildlife Fund for Nature

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Since the 1990s, the nexus between human rights and human development has received increasing attention in the context of development cooperation. With the emergence of the human rights-based approach (HRBA) to development in the early 21st century (UNDG, 2003), bilateral and international agencies increasingly acknowledged that human rights standards and principles should guide development cooperation. The adoption of feminist foreign and development policies by Sweden (2014-2022, see Towns et al., 2023), Canada (from 2017, see Global Affairs Canada, 2017), Germany (from 2023, see Federal Foreign Office of Germany, 2023; and BMZ, 2023a) and a few other countries has reiterated this commitment (Zilla, 2022).

The case for implementing human rights norms and principles as well as gender equality in development cooperation in general, and in the evaluation of development interventions in particular, is both normative and instrumental. The normative case for implementing human rights and gender equality is clear: most countries have ratified international human rights conventions, and have committed themselves to respecting, protecting and fulfilling these rights.

Therefore – despite long-standing and complex discussions about the universality of human rights (Mende, 2019; 2021) – these rights provide the major normative basis for joint efforts to incorporate human rights standards and principles in development cooperation. Good development interventions and the evaluation thereof should take this normative basis as a starting point, as well as actively contribute towards its progressive realisation. If development interventions and evaluations are not based on a joint normative basis, they are likely to be less useful (with utility being a widely shared norm of good evaluations, e.g., UNEG, 2016).

The instrumental reasoning for human rights-based evaluation focusses on data quality. Through a methodology that takes multiple perspectives into account, especially those of marginalised groups, human rights-based evaluations illuminate the evaluand from a broad range of angles. To draw reliable conclusions and recommendations, data should be collected systematically and include a diverse spectrum of perspectives. To ensure the broad participation of all relevant stakeholders, vulnerabilities must be understood and barriers to participation recognised. In this manner blind spots, bias and discrimination can actively be avoided (UNEG 2020: 16; UNEG 2016: 24). In its final declaration, the 1993 Vienna World Conference on Human Rights emphasised that the realisation of human rights and the associated adjustments to policies are only possible through the systematic analysis and use of indicators (OHCHR, 2025). Hence, the systematic inclusion of human rights can facilitate both effective development interventions and more functional evaluation (OHCHR, 2025).

Until 2011, guidance on how to operationalise an HRBA to development focused on the design and planning of development interventions. In 2011 UNEG framed the concept of the HRBA in the evaluation context and published a manual on how to integrate human rights and gender equality in evaluations in 2014 (UNEG, 2014).

The guidance has been a key reference document for human rights-based evaluations. It was updated in 2024 (UNEG, 2024) to incorporate more recent debates on human rights and gender in the evaluation context. In 2016, UNEG included a new norm on human rights and gender equality (Norm 8) in its “Norms and Standards for Evaluation” (UNEG, 2016). This boosted the mainstreaming of the HRBA to evaluation in the evaluation policies, strategies and standards of UN development agencies.

Between 2017 and 2019, the OECD DAC updated its five evaluation criteria, added a new criterion on “coherence” and opted to integrate human rights and gender equality into the assessment of the six criteria (OECD, 2019; 2021). The OECD DAC has recently published a guidance on how to apply a human rights and gender equality lens to the six criteria (OECD, 2023).

The UNEG (2014 and 2024) provides overarching guidance on how to design, plan and implement human rights and gender equality-responsive evaluations. The updated version highlights aspects of discrimination, with a particular focus on intersectional discrimination, discrimination against people with disabilities and in vulnerable situations (UNEG, 2024). The OECD (2023) guidance shows ways of applying a human rights and gender equality lens to evaluations along the six evaluation criteria. There are now a range of evaluation approaches in place that define themselves as human rights-based, gender-responsive or gender-transformative and which have been applied to evaluations.⁵

Despite these conceptual developments, the evaluation community is still discussing how to define what a human rights-based evaluation means and how it differs from standard evaluation practice.

The challenges in implementing a human rights-based evaluation are two-fold. Firstly, one needs to conceptualise what human rights-based evaluation is. What are the defining characteristics of a human rights-based evaluation in terms of minimum requirements? Also, do we need to differentiate between different types of human rights-based evaluation that go beyond these minimum requirements?

Second, how can we bridge potential gaps between the normative ambition to cover everything at once and the actual evaluation practice, which faces multiple limitations (e.g., resource constraints, organisational requirements, the legal and cultural context) in the real world. A recent review (Worm et al., 2022) showed that - despite existing guidelines and policies - evaluation practice is still lacking a systematic implementation of human rights. What are some feasible steps to systematically implement a human rights-based evaluation? Are there any good practices or practical guidelines that one can follow?

There is therefore a need to clarify the scope of human rights-based evaluation, as well as the potentials and challenges of implementing human rights and gender equality in the evaluation of development cooperation.

1.2 Objective and scope of the discussion paper

This paper contributes to the discussion on how to conceptualise human rights-based evaluations and how to incorporate human rights and gender equality in evaluation practice. It focuses on evaluations in bilateral development cooperation in the OECD DAC context.

Our main thesis is that although core human rights and gender equality norms and principles form the essence of any human rights-based evaluation, the intensity of applying them to the evaluation process may vary. Therefore, the key questions we would like to propose answers for are as follows:

- Why are human rights and gender equality relevant to the evaluation of development cooperation?
- How do the core human rights and gender equality concepts, standards and principles relate to the evaluation of development cooperation?
- How can core human rights principles be applied to key aspects of the evaluation process?
- How can different degrees of incorporating core human rights principles in the evaluation process be defined?
- How do core human rights principles relate to professional evaluation standards, and how do human rights-based evaluations differ from standard evaluation practice?

The discussion paper is divided into four chapters. After this introductory chapter, Chapter 2 defines the core human rights and gender equality concepts, standards and principles that form the basis of our understanding and conceptualisation of human rights-based evaluation. It introduces a scale to assess the degree to which development programmes incorporate human rights and gender equality and briefly

⁵ See for example AFD & DIHR (2023), BSR (2025), Dazzo (2022), DIHR (2020), Maschi (2016) on human rights based approaches to evaluation; Mertens (2009), Van den Berg et al. (2021) on transformative evaluation approaches; Brisolará et al. (2014), Global Affairs Canada (2024), Kelly & Stillo (2024), Podems (2010), and Wyatt et al. (2021) on feminist evaluation approaches.

describes the dynamic of human rights and gender equality in the face of new global commitments and difficulties. Chapter 3 deals with the implications of integrating human rights and gender equality in evaluation practice. It shows entry points, potentials and challenges for operationalising human rights principles in evaluations. It also introduces the Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale. The scale is used to illustrate how human rights principles can be structured and implemented for evaluation purposes along three different scale levels. Further, the extent to which human rights principles are compatible with professional evaluation standards are examined in this chapter. Finally, Chapter 3 briefly discusses how human rights principles can be applied in a flexible way in different types of evaluations. Chapter 4 summarises the findings and draws conclusions regarding human rights-based evaluation practice.

This paper is partly based on the findings of a review of human rights-based evaluation in international development by the same authors (Worm et al, 2022). The review analysed strategies and guidelines of development agencies, selected tools, academic and journal articles as well as 51 evaluation reports. It served as a starting point for a reflection process on how to conceptualise human rights and gender equality as quality criteria in evaluations.

Therefore, it does not offer solutions for all challenges but instead reflects our current thinking on how these challenges may be fruitfully approached. In the spirit of progressively implementing human rights in evaluations, it outlines how we aim to improve our evaluation practice and offer these reflections for others to adapt and for the evaluation community to critically appraise each other in their efforts of implementing human rights and gender-based evaluations.

2. CORE CONCEPTS

2.1 Human rights and gender equality: what do we really mean?

Human rights are fundamental rights and freedoms inherent to all human beings. They are enshrined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) and nine core UN human rights treaties, which are often complemented by regional conventions.

The nine core international human rights treaties include (a) the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR, 1966) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR, 1966), (b) conventions that specify and guarantee individual rights and freedoms, such as the Convention against Torture (CAT, 1984), and (c) conventions that set out the rights of groups particularly affected by discrimination, such as the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD, 2006). The African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (ACHPR, 1981) is an example of a regional convention.

Gender equality is a core human right enshrined in almost every human rights treaty. The ICCPR and the ICESCR oblige states in their common Article 3 to ensure that men and women equally enjoy all rights set out in both Covenants. The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW, 1979) defines specific measures to end discrimination based on gender and ensure equality between men and women.

Once states have ratified a human rights treaty, they are legally bound to **respect, protect and fulfil** these rights. This threefold obligation requires states:

- to refrain from interfering with or curtailing the enjoyment of human rights (obligation to respect).
- to protect individuals and groups against human rights abuses committed by other actors (obligation to protect).
- to take positive action to facilitate the enjoyment of human rights (obligation to fulfil).

International human rights law primarily determines the relationship between individuals and groups with entitlements (**rights-holders**) and state actors with correlative obligations (**duty-bearers**). The state and governmental institutions are the primary duty-bearers under international human rights law. However, international human rights law recognises that other actors also have obligations. For example, according to the Convention on the Rights of the Child, parents have specific duties and responsibilities towards their children (CRC, 1989).

According to international human rights law, business entities also have the obligation to respect human rights. Extraterritorial obligations require states to take steps to prevent and redress human rights infringements due to the activities of business entities over which they can exercise control (UN CESCR, 2017: 10). The UN Human Rights Council endorsed the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights in 2011. These principles clarify the duties of member states and the responsibilities of private companies regarding the realisation of human rights (OHCHR, 2011).

The ongoing debate on the extraterritorial scope of international human rights treaties extends to the role and responsibility of development cooperation (Wagner, 2017; Kämpf and Würth, 2010; Janig, 2021). The UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (UN CESCR) emphasised several general comments that international cooperation and assistance should be provided in a manner that is consistent with human rights standards (UN CESCR, 2003; 2008; 2009; 2016). The latest human rights treaty, the CRPD, states in article 36 that international cooperation should support the realisation of the covenant (CRPD, Art. 36).

2.2 What is the human rights-based approach to development?

Whereas the UN treaties and comments of the treaty bodies specify the content of human rights, they do not give specific guidance on how to incorporate human rights in development cooperation. The concept of a **human rights-based approach (HRBA) to development** emerged at the end of the Cold War in the 1990s.

A major milestone was the UN Statement of Common Understanding on a Human Rights-Based Approach to Development, which was endorsed by the United Nations Development Group (UNDG) in 2003.

As shown in Box 1, the first element of the HRBA to development relates to the **content** of development programmes, and also applies to evaluations. Therefore, evaluators need to assess the extent to which development programmes are consistent with and promote the realisation of human rights and gender equality.

The second element relates to the programming and management cycle in development cooperation, and thereby to the **process** of development cooperation. It implies that evaluators incorporate human rights standards and principles in the evaluation process and the way evaluations are implemented. As a third element, development programmes should contribute towards capacity development efforts to establish power relationships that enable duty-bearers to guarantee, realise and protect human rights, as well as enable rights-holders to claim their rights.

Box 1 The UN Common Understanding on a HRBA to Development Cooperation

- All programmes of development cooperation, policies and technical assistance should further the realisation of human rights as laid down in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and other international human rights instruments.
- Human rights standards contained in, and principles derived from, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and other international human rights instruments guide all development cooperation and programming in all sectors and in all phases of the programming process.
- Development cooperation contributes to the development of the capacities of “duty-bearers” to meet their obligations and/or of “rights-holders” to claim their rights.

Source: UNDG, 2003: 1

Several bilateral donors and agencies, including Germany, have adopted human rights policies and strategies that call for mainstreaming an HRBA to development by systematically integrating human rights standards and principles into development cooperation (World Bank & OECD, 2016). These strategies are oriented towards the UN understanding of an HRBA and focus primarily on three human rights principles: non-discrimination, participation and accountability. For example, the human rights strategy of the BMZ refers to the core human rights principles as “non-discrimination and equal opportunities”, “participation and empowerment” and “transparency and accountability” (BMZ, 2023b: 12).

In recent years, both gender equality and human rights-based development strategies have emphasised the aim of achieving transformative change by addressing and overcoming the root causes of inequalities, such as, for example discriminatory laws, norms, practices or attitudes. Transformative approaches strive to positively transform power relationships and societal dynamics that perpetuate gender inequalities and the discrimination of marginalised population groups (OECD, 2023; BMZ, 2023a and 2023b).

Summing up, a human rights-based approach to development has three key elements:

- The content of development interventions should be consistent with human rights standards.
- The process of development interventions should reflect and incorporate human rights principles.
- Development interventions should aim at transformative change.

2.3 How can we assess the gender equality and human rights orientation of development programmes?

The degree to which development programmes address, promote and achieve gender equality and human rights varies greatly in practice. Therefore, multilateral and bilateral agencies have developed and applied assessment scales to assess the degree to which development programmes incorporate human rights and gender equality.

The “gender integration continuum” scale (WHO, 2011; Save the Children, 2014; UNICEF, 2021) differentiates between the following degrees: gender-discriminatory, gender-unaware, gender-sensitive, gender-responsive and gender-transformative (see Figure 1).

Finland’s guidance on a human rights-based approach to development includes an assessment scale, with four levels ranging from “human rights-blind”⁶ to “human rights-transformative” interventions (MFAF, 2015: 8). Figure 1 shows the elements that are most relevant to the evaluation context.

Both scales are similar and complement each other. The gender integration continuum focuses on gender equality as a core human right. The Finnish scale addresses human rights in a generic way. Both scales describe a progression from interventions that do not consider human rights and gender equality to interventions that seek to transform societal relations and power dynamics and eliminate discrimination. Gender sensitivity is a core requirement for all interventions.

Beyond this minimal standard, interventions should strive to be gender-responsive or gender-transformative (OECD, 2022). However, even an intervention that has gender equality as its core objective may be gender-transformative in some respects and gender-sensitive or -responsive in others.

The Finnish human rights scale helps to define core characteristics and minimal standards for human rights-based evaluations. In our view, a human rights-based evaluation must be at least human rights-sensitive, i.e. evaluators should explicitly mention which human rights are relevant for the evaluation content and explain which human rights principles guide the evaluation process.

Beyond this core requirement, human rights-based evaluations may vary in terms of how human rights principles are applied to the evaluation process. Therefore, an evaluation may be sensitive in some phases or aspects of the evaluation and responsive or transformative in others. Human rights-based evaluations should therefore be understood as a quality criterion for evaluations rather than a methodological approach. In subsequent chapters, we show how the human rights scale can be applied to each human rights principle in the evaluation process.

⁶ We strive to use non-discriminatory language and avoid stigmatising and derogatory terms. The use of the term “human rights-blind” here results from the citation of the source given.

Figure 1 Comparison of gender and human right scales

Source: DEval, own visualisation

2.4 What are the key human rights principles and standards?

In the development context, human rights standards refer to the content of specific human rights, while human rights principles relate to the process by which human rights are put into practice. The following chapter introduces the core human rights principles and standards that are the most relevant in the HRBA and clarify their relevance in the evaluation context.⁷

The HRBA to development embraces core human rights issues such as gender equality, the inclusion of persons with disabilities, child rights or the rights of LGBTIQ+ persons. Its normative background consists of the core UN human rights treaties and the interpretation of independent experts, who are part of the ten UN treaty bodies, or the special procedures of the Human Rights Council. The independent experts define the content of human rights in the general comments as well as the core human rights principles and standards.

The general comments issued by the treaty bodies are not binding legal documents but are considered as an authoritative interpretation of specific human rights and treaties. Furthermore, independent experts are also appointed by the Human Rights Council with the mandate to report and advise on specific human rights. Their thematic studies contribute to the development of international human rights standards and principles.

Participation is a human right enshrined in international human rights treaties, such as the right to take part in the conduct of public affairs (ICCPR, Art. 25), the right of women to participate in political and public life (CEDAW, Art. 7) or the right of persons with disabilities to effectively and fully participate in political and public life on an equal basis with others (CRPD, Art. 29).

The UN Declaration on the Right to Development (1986) defines participation as the “active, free and meaningful participation of all individuals in development” (Art. 2). Participation is also a key principle of the HRBA to development. It requires development cooperation to promote opportunities for rights-holders, particularly marginalised individuals and groups, to be informed about and have an influence on the evaluation process.

The guidelines of the UN Special Rapporteur on the practical implementation of the right to development emphasise the importance of “meaningful” participation, which should “serve as a basis for assessing what rights-holders’ interests are and ensure those interests are met” (OHCHR, 2020: 5).

Meaningful participation goes beyond the mere consultation of individuals and communities to gather information. It implies involving rights-holders in and putting them at the centre of decision-making processes which affect their own economic, social, cultural and political development. Ultimately, it aims to empower them to claim and realise their rights (OHCHR, 2006; UN Human Rights Special Procedures, 2020; Kayser & Osterhaus, 2014).

The principle of **non-discrimination** is included in all international human rights treaties. For example, Art. 2 of the ICESCR states that “the States Parties to the present Covenant undertake to guarantee that the rights enunciated in the present Covenant will be exercised without discrimination of any kind as to race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status”. International human rights law distinguishes between **discrimination by law** (for example inheritance laws that discriminate against women) and **discrimination in practice** (for example unequal access of persons with disabilities to the labour market).

⁷ In this paper, we focus on the human rights principles of transparency and accountability, non-discrimination and equality of opportunities as well as empowerment and participation. These principles guide German development cooperation. In addition to these principles, there are other principles that are linked to human rights-based approaches, e.g. accessibility, intersectionality or fair power relations. However, the team of authors holds that other principles can be assigned to the three pairs of principles, e.g. accessibility and intersectionality are essential aspects of non-discrimination and fair power relations are included in the concept of empowerment. The authors believe that the possible inclusion of other human rights principles in the principles presented in this paper provides a sufficiently broad framework for a comprehensive human rights-based approach.

Therefore, states have the obligation to abolish discriminatory laws and take measures against prevalent discriminatory attitudes, practices and stigmas (CESCR, 2009). Recent treaties (CRPD, CRC) convey both a legal (equality before and under the law) and a social vision (de facto equality of opportunities in society). Gender equality is a core dimension of non-discrimination. Treaty bodies and independent human rights experts have interpreted the prohibition of discrimination as to include discrimination on the ground of sexual orientation and gender identity (CESCR, 2009; OHCHR, 2019).

The HRBA to development aims to overcome de jure and de facto patterns of discrimination by addressing the underlying causes of inequalities and exclusion. This can be achieved either by fostering inclusive processes that set a focus on dismantling access barriers, or by specific measures to promote and realise the rights of marginalised or discriminated groups (BMZ, 2023b; OHCHR, 2006).

Programming, monitoring and evaluating human rights-based development measures therefore requires appropriate disaggregated data to be able to identify discriminated and marginalised groups and assess the impact of measures to overcome discrimination (OHCHR, 2018). Simultaneously, evaluations ought to be designed in such a way that they do not reproduce existing structures of discrimination.

All human rights treaties require member states to undertake steps to realise rights (see for example ICCPR, Art.2; ICESCR, Art. 2). **Accountability** is defined as the process by which states and governments show, explain and justify how they have complied with their human rights obligations. Individuals and groups should have the opportunity and capacity to request explanations from the government on the measures it has taken or not taken (Potts, 2008).

Accountability includes the right to remedies if a right has been violated (ICCPR, Art.2). Remedies can take different judicial and non-judicial forms, including restitution, rehabilitation, compensation or satisfaction and guarantees of non-repetition (CESR, 2017).

Human rights experts differentiate between the following types of accountability mechanisms: judicial (e.g., constitutional courts), quasi-judicial (e.g., UN treaty bodies), administrative (e.g., human rights impact assessments), political (e.g., parliamentary committees) and social (e.g., social audits and public hearings) (Potts, 2008).

The HRBA to development delegates accountability to the actors responsible for carrying out development interventions within a framework of specific human rights entitlements and the corresponding obligations established under international human rights law. This implies that development aid should contribute to enhancing the capacity of government partners to comply with their obligations. Effective monitoring and evaluation mechanisms strengthen the ability of governments to assess their human rights performance and be accountable to rights-holders.

Accountability in the context of development cooperation thus has two major aspects. The first aspect derives from the obligation of states to protect and respect human rights: development cooperation interventions should not have negative impacts on human rights (CESCR, 1990; Kämpf & Würth, 2010). If development cooperation measures contribute to violating rights, rights-holders should be entitled to institute proceedings for appropriate redress (UNDG, 2003, Pott, 2008).

Both obligations are closely related to the principles of “human rights due diligence” and “do no harm”. Governments and business entities should identify, prevent and mitigate the risks of human rights violations resulting from their activities (CESCR, 2017; OHCHR, 2011). In the context of development cooperation, “do no harm” also applies to the ethical code of conduct of development professionals, evaluators and researchers. Their conduct should not harm the individuals or groups involved in the research, data collection or evaluation process (Kaplan et al., 2019; OHCHR, 2018; Ulrich, 2018).

The second major aspect derives from the obligation of states to fulfil human rights. International human rights law differentiates between immediate obligations and obligations that can be fulfilled over a certain period. States have an immediate obligation to fulfil civil and political rights and to ensure that minimum levels of social and economic rights are realised without discrimination.

Besides these immediate obligations, economic, social and cultural rights are subject to the principle of **progressive realisation**: “Each State Party to the present Covenant undertakes to take steps, individually and through international assistance and co-operation, especially economic and technical, to the maximum of its available resources, with a view to achieving progressively the full realisation of the rights recognised in the present Covenant by all appropriate means, including particularly the adoption of legislative measures” (ICESCR, Art. 2.1). This principle implies that development cooperation should support partner governments to progressively realise social and economic rights.

Accountability in the HRBA to development, as understood by bilateral development aid agencies, goes hand in hand with the principle of **transparency** (BMZ, 2023b).

Transparency is closely linked to the right to seek, receive and impart information, which is guaranteed in the ICCPR (Art. 19) and other treaties (for example CRPD, Art. 21; ICMW, Art. 13). States are obliged to inform citizens and residents about their rights and the measures taken by the government to fulfil these rights. In the context of development cooperation and evaluation it is particularly relevant for all processes of data collection and dissemination, including monitoring and evaluation.

On the one hand, it requires rights-holders to have access to information, data and reports in an accessible language and format (OHCHR, 2018). On the other hand, data collection should respect confidentiality and the principle of voluntary informed consent, which includes the right of individuals to be properly informed and to freely determine whether they want to be involved in research activities, surveys or interviews (OHCHR, 2018; Ulrich, 2017).

The content of specific human rights and respective standards are laid down in the general comments and reports of the independent human rights experts. For example, the CESCR has elaborated the following categories to define the content of many social and economic rights: availability, accessibility, acceptability, and quality. The so-called AAAQ framework constitutes a yardstick to assess the extent to which states are on the right track to complying with their obligations. Table 1 provides an example of the AAAQ framework as related to health rights.

Table 1 AAAQ framework and health rights

Core elements	Content
Availability	Adequate functioning health facilities and services as well as essential medicines; availability of safe drinking water and adequate sanitation facilities.
Accessibility	<p>Accessibility of health facilities and services for all, without discrimination:</p> <p>Physical accessibility and safe access for all, including vulnerable persons and groups (e.g., persons with disabilities).</p> <p>Information accessibility, i.e. the right to seek, receive and impart health information whilst respecting the confidentiality of data. Information should be provided in accessible formats, i.e. easily understood by all.</p> <p>Information must be provided in a manner consistent with the needs of the individual and the community, for example taking into consideration age, gender, language ability, educational level, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity and intersex status.</p> <p>Affordability for all, and specifically for poor and vulnerable population groups.</p>
Acceptability	<p>Respect of medical ethics, including the principles of informed consent and confidentiality as well as cultural appropriateness.</p> <p>All health information and services must be respectful of the culture of individuals, minorities, peoples and communities, and sensitive to gender, age, disability, sexual diversity and life-cycle requirements. However, this cannot be used to justify the refusal to provide services to specific groups.</p>
Quality	Scientifically and medically appropriate services of good quality, including skilled health personnel, scientifically approved and unexpired drugs and medical equipment.

Source: Adapted from General Comment No. 14 (2000) on the right to the highest attainable standard of health in Article 12 of the ICESCR by the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR, 2000) and General Comment No. 22 (2016) on the right to sexual and reproductive health (CESCR, 2016).

The AAAQ framework serves as a guide for how evaluations can be conducted. For example, evaluations can examine development interventions as to whether AAAQ has been implemented or considered.

2.5 Why is the dynamic of human rights and the HRBA to development important?

International human rights law and the HRBA to development are not static concepts, but follow the dynamic of societal changes, global crises and challenges. For example, the most recent UN treaty, the CRPD (2006), is an outcome of the struggle led by persons with disabilities to affirm their rights.

Human rights institutions, experts and activists were also actively involved in the debate that led to the adoption of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The resolution adopted by the UN General Assembly in September 2015 incorporates the human rights vision: “We are determined to take the bold and transformative steps which are urgently needed to shift the world on to a sustainable and resilient path. As we embark on this collective journey, we pledge that no one will be left behind (...) The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (...) seek to realise the human rights of all and to achieve gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls” (UN, 2015).

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were under strong criticism by the human rights community for their focus on average progress and their inadequacy to capture inequalities (OHCHR, 2008). The 2030 Agenda reflects the evolving nature of international commitments towards integrating human rights in the development agenda (Arts, 2017; Saiz & Donald, 2017; Jägers, 2020). The SDG framework includes stand-

alone goals on reducing inequality (SDG 10), gender equality and the empowerment of women and girls (SDG 5). Various targets and indicators also reflect human rights aspects.

The overarching Leave No One Behind (LNOB) principle of the 2030 Agenda emphasises the importance of including marginalised groups in the development process. The notion of inclusive development has gained importance since the adoption of the 2030 Agenda, thus strengthening a human rights perspective in the development discourse (Arts, 2017).

However, whether addressing the LNOB principle means the same as tackling discrimination and intersectional inequalities on human rights grounds remains a matter of debate (Saiz and Donald, 2017). Human rights experts also argue that while the 2030 Agenda acknowledges the importance of the private sector for sustainable development, it does not pay sufficient attention to human rights due diligence, i.e. the responsibility of private companies to respect human rights and to avoid negative impacts resulting from business activities (Jägers, 2020).

Although the implementation of national SDG strategies and of the ratified human rights conventions are subject to different monitoring, review and follow-up mechanisms, opportunities do exist to enhance synergies between both the SDG and the human rights monitoring system (The Danish Institute for Human Rights, 2020).

As mentioned above, gender equality between women and men is a core human rights concept enshrined in almost every human rights treaty. Gender equality strategies in development cooperation have also emphasised women's rights and the empowerment of girls and women. More recently, the understanding of the gender concept has evolved beyond the binary perception of gender roles to include diverse gender identities.

For example, in 2020 and 2021 the European Council (EC) and the German government each issued their first equality strategies for diverse gender identities (LGBTQI+) (Federal Foreign Office & Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2021; EC, 2020). Canada, France and Germany currently have a "feminist development policy" (BMZ, 2023a; Global Affairs Canada, 2017; Ministère de l'Europe et des Affaires Étrangères, 2025). These policies build on previous gender equality and human rights strategies. They aim at eliminating structural inequalities, unequal treatment and discrimination by realising the rights and improving the representation of women, girls, LGBTQI+ persons and other marginalised groups.

A similar dynamic has taken place in the international human rights system. The human rights community is increasingly involved in the debate on gender diversity and the rights of LGBTQI+ persons. In 2016, the UN Human Rights Council created the mandate of the Independent Expert on sexual orientation and gender identity to explore ways to overcome violence and discrimination against persons based on their sexual orientation or gender identity (UN Human Rights Council, 2016).

Environmental aspects are included in rights such as the right to water, health or an adequate standard of living. However, as yet there is no international human rights treaty that specifies the content of environmental rights in the context of climate change. The climate crisis has boosted the debate on the accountability of states and businesses for negative impacts on the climate, as well as on the obligation to adopt adequate mitigation measures that respect the human rights of individuals and groups (UN Human Rights Council, 2019, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Arts, 2017).

Intergenerational equity is a concept that is increasingly gaining in importance in the face of the current climate crisis and the engagement of young people to affirm their rights and the rights of future generations to a sustainable environment (OHCHR, 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic has also triggered a debate on human rights issues, such as the effects of the pandemic and the respective measures on civil and political rights (Action Aid, 2021), the rights of marginalised groups (UN, 2020) and global vaccine equity (Torrele and Ammon, 2021; WHO 2021).

3. PROGRESSIVELY IMPLEMENTING HUMAN RIGHTS AND GENDER EQUALITY IN EVALUATION PRACTICE

This chapter discusses the entry points and the challenges of applying human rights standards and principles in evaluation practice. Based on existing guidance, Chapter 3.1 provides an overview of the overall framework and the core elements of human rights-based evaluations.

Chapter 3.2 to 3.5 focus on selected aspects of the evaluation process and the core human rights principles of participation and empowerment, non-discrimination and equality of opportunities, as well as accountability and transparency. For each principle, they outline different degrees of implementing human rights principles in the evaluation process.

To this end, we have adapted the Finnish human rights scale (see Chapter 2.3) and applied the categories “human rights-sensitive”, “human rights-responsive” and “human rights-transformative” to the evaluation context. We did not consider the category of “human rights-unaware”, as such an evaluation cannot be considered as human rights-based and would not comply with basic professional evaluation standards. As a result, we present the Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale (HRIIS) in the following chapter. The HRIIS allows to evaluate the application of each principle on a scale of three degrees.

For each aspect of the evaluation, we suggest central characteristics of a human rights-sensitive, responsive and transformative evaluation. These characteristics are meant to provide heuristic guidance as to what the different levels imply. These suggestions are, of course, open to critique and may be refined over time.

Both the Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale and the three elements of human rights-based approaches – content, process and transformative aim – serve as central orientation points to progressively implement human rights and gender into evaluations.

3.1 How to find the suitable level of intensity for a human rights-based evaluation?

The three elements of a human rights-based approach to development outlined in Chapter 2.2 (content, process and transformative aim) may also apply to evaluations: (1) applying human rights and gender equality to the **content** and object of the evaluation; (2) incorporating core human rights principles into the evaluation **process**, and (3) contributing with evaluations to the **transformation** of power relationships and the realisation of human rights and gender equality.

The OECD DAC publication on applying a human rights and gender equality lens to the six standard evaluation criteria primarily focuses on how to integrate human rights into the **content** of evaluations (OECD, 2023). It interprets each evaluation criterion through a human rights and gender equality lens, suggests elements of analysis and provides examples that illustrate different ways in which human rights and gender equality have been applied to the criteria (OECD, 2023).

Figure 2 provides a summary of how to interpret the evaluation criteria with a human rights and gender equality lens.

Figure 2 Interpretation of the OECD DAC evaluation criteria (adapted from OECD (2023))

Source: DEval, own visualisation

Both multilateral (e.g., UNDP, 2021; UNICEF, 2017a; UNFPA, 2019) and bilateral agencies (e.g., BMZ, 2021; MFAD, 2018; EDA, 2018; MFAF, 2020; SIDA, 2020, Spanish Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Cooperation, 2013) also refer to human rights and gender equality in their evaluation policies and guidelines.

The UNEG guidance focuses on how to integrate human rights and gender equality in the evaluation **process** (UNEG, 2024). Figure 3 gives an overview of the key elements of applying human rights and gender equality to different phases of the evaluation process, as recommended by the UNEG guidance.

Figure 3 UNEG guidance on human rights and gender equality (HR and GE) in the evaluation process (adapted from UNEG, 2014, Chapters 4-7)

Source: DEval, own visualisation

The third aspect, i.e. the **transformative aim** of evaluations, is related both to the content and to the process of evaluations. However, not every evaluation can always follow a transformative aim or even be a human rights-transformative evaluation regarding all aspects of the evaluation. Neither is this feasible or even always purposeful.

Introducing the Human Rights Intensity Scale

In order to deal with the intensity of the integration of human rights principles and standards in a systematic way, as well as, being transparent about the integration of human rights in an evaluation and finding a terminology which further developments and debates in the field of human rights-based evaluation can be based on, we propose establishing the use of three different levels of human rights-based evaluation. Derived from the scales mentioned above (MFAF, 2015; Save the Children, 2014; UNICEF, 2021; WHO, 2011) it is possible to define some core characteristics of human rights-sensitive, human rights-responsive and human rights-transformative evaluations. These levels are shown in the Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale.

Figure 4 The Human Rights Integration Intensity Scale

Source: DEval, own visualisation

The HRIIS is intended to be understood in a regulatory logic that focuses on the real world application of human rights and gender equality in evaluation. Analogous to a mixing board, the intensity level for each pair of principles can be adjusted depending on the evaluation object, the goals of the evaluation, and the resources available for the evaluation. The intensity level of the integration of human rights and gender can vary from evaluation to evaluation. Ideally, each evaluation should start with an assessment of which principles can be implemented and to what extent this is both desirable and feasible. From a human rights perspective, more ambitious levels are desirable, but from a perspective acknowledging the progressive realization of human rights principles and standards, it is also acceptable if a principle cannot be implemented at the highest conceivable level, but at the highest level appropriate to the circumstances. A clear and transparent description of the decisions made is therefore important.

The individual levels are described in more detail below, with explanations of their purpose and ideas for their possible implementation.

Purpose and implementation of the different levels

The purpose of the human rights-sensitive level is analysing human rights aspects of an evaluation and to critically reflect on these for the evaluation context. In a human rights-sensitive evaluation, evaluators would, for example

- analyse which human rights are relevant for the evaluation, and explicitly mention these rights in the evaluation report
- assess who are the duty-bearers and who are the rights-holders in the evaluation context
- briefly explain which human rights principles guide the evaluation process

The main objective of responsive evaluation is not only to reflect about human rights in the evaluation context, but to systematically analyse and consider human rights issues in the evaluation. In a human rights-responsive evaluation, the evaluator should, for example,

- conduct a deeper analysis of the extent to which the intervention contributes to the realisation of human rights
- explain the degree to which human rights principles guide the different phases of the evaluation process

If the purpose of an evaluation is to contribute to the transformation of power relationships and the realisation of human rights, it should fully incorporate human rights norms, standards and principles in the content, the analytical framework and in the evaluation process.

Seen through this lens, in a human rights-transformative evaluation evaluators would assess the extent to which an intervention strengthens the capacity of

- duty-bearers to meet their human rights obligations, i.e., to respect, protect and fulfil human rights (accountability)
- duty-bearers to overcome structural inequalities, eliminate the root causes of discrimination and include marginalised groups in development processes (non-discrimination)
- rights-holders to claim and realise their rights (participation and empowerment)

In practice, strategic evaluations of bilateral development interventions rarely aim to transform power relationships and empower rights-holders to claim their rights explicitly (Worm et al., 2022). However, even if such evaluations do not fully “qualify” as gender or human rights-transformative, they may incorporate transformative elements in some aspects of the evaluation process.

3.2 What are the key aspects in the design of human rights-based evaluations?

The following chapter shows how to consider different intensity levels (sensitive, responsive, transformative) in the design of evaluations.

Identifying the relevant human rights and core principles to address in evaluations

Most development interventions relate to several interlinked rights (e.g., the right to health with the right to education). Identifying the relevant rights addressed by the intervention is indispensable for an adequate assessment of relevance, and provides the basis for assessments of effectiveness, impact and sustainability. However, it is not feasible to consider all rights in one evaluation design.

In a **human rights-sensitive** evaluation, evaluators identify the major rights addressed by the intervention. The evaluation focuses on the most relevant right, for example by taking gender equality into consideration. It considers the role of socio-cultural norms (including gendered norms) and the needs of different groups of rights-holders. In a **human rights-responsive** evaluation, evaluators consider the interdependency of rights and conceptualise these links in the evaluation questions.

In a **human rights-transformative** evaluation there is a strong focus on the indivisibility and interdependency of human rights, the assessment of how the intervention contributes to changing socio-cultural norms (including gendered norms), and the realisation of rights beyond the major right addressed by the intervention.

Likewise, the core human rights principles are interlinked. Therefore, it is necessary to define in human rights-based evaluations how the intervention relates to the core human rights principles. Depending on the object, purpose and intended use of the evaluation, it appears legitimate to assess one or two principles in depth.

If, for example, an evaluation assesses a development intervention that supports and works with rights-holders and civil society organisations representing them, participation and empowerment may constitute a key aspect. If an evaluation assesses a programme that promotes reproductive health and rights, non-discrimination and the inclusion of marginalised groups and persons with diverse gender identities would most probably be a key aspect. If an evaluation assesses a programme that supports the development of water and sanitation systems, the accountability of governments to (progressively) realise the respective rights involved could be an essential aspect. If an evaluation is conducted in response to allegations of human rights abuses caused by a development cooperation intervention, accountability and human rights due diligence would certainly constitute a core evaluation issue.

The latter evaluation could also be used by rights-holders and their representatives to claim their right to remedies and redress. Once evaluators have determined which principles should be assessed in-depth, they need to define what these principles mean in the context of the evaluated intervention and integrate them into guiding questions (see OECD, 2023, for suggested evaluation questions related to the six OECD DAC evaluation criteria).

Box 2 Examples of guiding evaluation questions incorporating human rights principles

- Norad’s evaluation of Norway’s International Climate and Forest Initiatives focuses on the empowerment of indigenous groups. Empowerment is defined as “the extent to which indigenous people and other forest-dependent communities, men and women, can demand their rights and representation and/or have the right to effectively participate in decision-making processes concerning the ownership/allocation of resources, or gaining access to information and training to develop local organisational capacity and accountability, among others” (Norad, 2017: 10).
- One of the guiding questions addresses coherence: “What have been the motivation, objectives and strategies of Norway’s International Climate and Forest Initiative and the Civil Society Department of Norad for empowering forest-dependent local communities, and how are these linked to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs’ overall policy for supporting the rights of indigenous people?” (Norad, 2017: 60).
- Under the sustainability criterion, a guiding question of UN Women’s evaluation on engaging women in preventing and countering extremist violence in Kenya was “How will the benefits of the intervention be secured for rights-holders, i.e. what accountability and oversight systems were established?” (UN Women, 2017: 47).
- Amnesty International mandated an independent evaluation to assess the performance of its Education Empowerment Justice Programme, a five-year human rights education programme (2013–2017) that was implemented in 24 countries in Europe, Latin America, the Middle East and North Africa, Africa and Asia. The evaluation framework includes a set of key questions on empowerment. For example: “What factors have contributed to positive changes in empowerment, and what factors have limited the progress made?” or “What has been learned about empowerment that has implications for future activities in human rights education?” (AI, 2017: 4).

Reflecting human rights and gender equality in the theory of change

Reconstructing a theory of change and visualising pathways of change is a standard element of most evaluation designs. Correctly reconstructing a theory of change – including its relationship to human rights and gender equality – is necessary to ensure the credibility of an evaluation. Depending on the purpose and object of the evaluation, a **human rights-sensitive** design primarily includes human rights and gender equality as relevant context factors (e.g., to identify marginalised groups for whom effects of the intervention might be different). A **human rights-responsive** design theorises human rights and gender equality aspects mainly at the output and outcome levels. A **human rights-transformative** evaluation design conceptualises pathways of change that thoroughly reflect the intended effects on human rights and gender equality, as well as the transformation of power dynamics between rights-holders and duty-bearers at all levels of the ToC, including the impact level.

Box 3 Human rights and gender equality in theories of change

- The ToC of the evaluation of UNFPA’s support for the prevention of, response to and elimination of gender-based violence and harmful practices includes a legal, policy and institutional environment at the outcome level reflecting international human rights instruments as well as inclusive participation in decision-making. (UNFPA, 2018: 17).
- The ToC of the evaluation of UN Women’s contribution to promoting and protecting women migrant workers’ labour and human rights depicts a results chain leading from advocacy and capacity-building (inputs) to the accessibility of human rights-based and gender-responsive services (outcomes) for women migrant workers (Arbulu, 2017: 16).
- The evaluation of Oxfam’s multi-country programme on the health and education rights of children and young people describes the intended outcomes on rights-holders (e.g., the capacity of young people to articulate their needs and claim their right) and duty-bearers (e.g., their capacity to take specific actions to improve the access and quality of health and education services for boys and girls, young women and men) (Oxfam, 2016: 90).
- The ToC of the evaluations conducted by Brot für die Welt (Bread for the World) and Misereor on the human rights work of faith-based partner NGOs define and visualise outcomes such as the enhanced awareness of rights-holders and their capacity to claim rights as well as, on the duty-bearer’s side, an enhanced capacity to comply with international and regional human rights standards and mechanisms (Raab & Rocha, 2018; Stahl et al., 2018).

3.3 How to set the stage in the evaluation process?

Stakeholder assessment

Analysing the key stakeholders of an intervention and its evaluation forms part of the evaluability assessment and design of an evaluation. From a human rights perspective, a stakeholder analysis includes identifying who the rights-holders and the duty-bearers are (see Chapter 2). This provides the basis for a fair, ethical and impartial evaluation process. In evaluation practice this is a challenge, as the planning or monitoring documents of the development interventions that are being evaluated rarely use human rights terminology to describe the stakeholders.

Furthermore, whether a stakeholder should be considered as a rights-holder or a duty-bearer depends on the context and object of the intervention. For example, a teacher could be a rights-holder in a project aiming at improving the working conditions of employees in the education sector. Likewise, he/she could be a duty-bearer in a project aiming to improve the participation of school children.

The following categories may help to identify the relevant duty-bearers and rights-holders in a stakeholder assessment.

Box 4 Types of duty-bearers and rights-holders in evaluations of development cooperation

- **Primary duty-bearers:** Governmental institutions in partner countries that have the obligation to respect, protect and fulfil the rights that are relevant for the development intervention; governmental institutions and development cooperation agencies that have the obligation to support partner governments and institutions to implement these rights.
- **Secondary duty-bearers:** Other implementing or cooperation partners of development institutions who have specific duties and responsibilities, for example private-sector companies.
- **Primary rights-holders:** All individuals and groups that hold rights in the context of the development intervention and are targeted by the intervention.
- **Secondary rights-holders:** All rights-holders in the country whose rights may be positively or negatively affected by the intervention without them being directly targeted by the intervention.
- **Marginalised rights-holders:** Rights-holders who are discriminated against or at risk of being discriminated against in the context of the intervention.

Sources: Adapted from UNEG (2014) and Polak, J.T. et al. (2021)

In a **human rights-sensitive** design, evaluators identify who are the primary rights-holders targeted by the intervention and which groups of rights-holders are marginalised in the stakeholder assessment. They also identify the duty-bearers and their obligations towards rights-holders. In a **human rights-responsive** design, evaluators outline the situation of different groups of primary and secondary rights-holders. They identify marginalised groups of rights-holders, including potential intersectional links, e.g. between poverty and disability. In a **human rights-transformative** design, evaluators conduct a deeper assessment of all rights-holders and duty-bearers. It analyses the power dynamics between right-holders and duty-bearers, the root causes which lead to marginalisation as well as gender dynamics and intersectionality. A vulnerability analysis is a useful tool to identify marginalised groups and intersectional aspects (see Chapter 3.4.2). It can be applied to the responsive as well as to the transformative level, depending on the intensity of the analysis.

Composition of the team and the required expertise of team members

Implementing human rights and gender equality in evaluations requires the evaluation team to have sufficient experience and expertise. Diverse perspectives and relevant competencies increase the credibility, acceptance and ultimately the utility of the evaluation. The kinds of experiences and the levels of expertise required depend on the evaluation and the degree to which human rights are incorporated into the evaluation.

Human rights and gender-sensitive evaluations should be conducted by gender-balanced teams, including regional, national or local experts (UNEG, 2024). In a **human rights-sensitive** evaluation, evaluators can identify the relevant rights related to or addressed by the intervention and refer to the respective human rights treaties and interpretation of the UN treaty bodies.

Regional and national expertise is often needed to analyse the extent to which an intervention is coherent within the regional and national legal and policy frameworks on human rights and gender equality. Furthermore, **human rights-responsive** and particularly **human rights-transformative** evaluations demand sufficient social science and methodological expertise to identify and assess intersectional issues. This is challenging both in qualitative case-based designs as well as quantitative large-N designs.

Combining both content and methodological expertise within the team is often a challenge and requires sufficient time for the team to reach a consensus on the approach to be adopted as well as the respective tasks of the team members (see also Chapter 3.4.1 on the participation of rights-holders in the evaluation team).

3.4 How can human rights principles gradually be implemented in the evaluation process?

In the following chapters, we consider each core human rights principle and show how it can be implemented in a human rights-based evaluation process.

3.4.1 Participation and empowerment

According to the human rights-based definition, meaningful participation goes beyond merely consulting the stakeholders (rights-holders and duty-bearers) in a development intervention (see Chapter 2.2). It implies that rights-holders are more substantially involved in the evaluation process. In our view, beyond merely consulting the rights-holders, there are different levels of involving them in the evaluation process and ensuring their meaningful participation.

Meaningful participation can increase ownership and utility – by giving voice to those who may usually be marginalised, it can also have an empowering effect. Meaningfully involving rights-holders in evaluations gives them more voice to raise their concerns. Transparent communication and authentic dialogue with rights-holders on the limitations of evaluations (and of development programmes) may enable both better understanding of the evaluand by the evaluators and increased ownership of rights-holders regarding the results of the evaluation.

However, participation must be balanced against the evaluation norms of independence and impartiality. Defining meaningful participation in the context of a specific evaluation must address and balance this potential tension. This tension may be particularly prominent in the case of a human rights-transformative evaluation because questioning power hierarchies is part of the objective of such an evaluation and may only be possible when participation deeply involves rights-holders in designing and implementing the evaluation process thereby compromising an independent and impartial positioning of evaluators (see Figure 5).

UNICEF has published a guide that discusses the different ways in which children can participate in impact evaluations (Guijt, 2014). The guide is also helpful in reflecting on options for meaningful participation and the involvement of rights-holders, including marginalised groups, in other evaluations of development cooperation interventions. Figure 5 highlights the implications of different types of participation on the involvement of rights-holders in the evaluation process.

Figure 5 Types of participation of rights-holders in the evaluation process

Source: DEval, own visualisation

The first type – **nominal participation** – is frequently encountered in evaluations of development cooperation interventions. It is not fully compatible with the human rights definition of *meaningful* participation, insofar as rights-holders are mainly involved as providers of information. In accordance with the established evaluation standards, quantitative and qualitative data collection methods must respect confidentiality and the principle of voluntary informed consent.

Ethical principles and codes of conduct must be respected by the evaluation team throughout the evaluation to avoid causing harm to rights-holders who contribute their data (see e.g. TRUST, 2018). Ensuring that both relationships and communication remain fair between evaluators and the rights-holders consulted in these evaluations is a challenge. There is an ongoing debate about the practice of collecting and using data from countries in the Global South or from marginalised communities without compensating them fairly and giving them control over their data (Castillo, 2023; Godrie, 2025; Udah, 2024). Evaluators should consider how rights-holders can obtain a fair benefit from sharing information and their time with the evaluators (potentially including financial compensation). As minimal standard, consulted rights-holders must be informed about the purpose of the evaluation and the interviews carried out, and must have access to the findings of the evaluation.

The second type – **instrumental participation** – implies that rights-holders, who are the intended beneficiaries of an intervention, are involved as facilitators in the data collection process or as members of the evaluation team. These could, for example, be active members or civil society organisations representing the interests of marginalised groups.

Evaluation practice shows that involving rights-holders belonging to a marginalised group in the evaluation team on equal terms may bring added value for the evaluation process but does not come without challenges. On the one hand, they have easier access to members of their own peer group, and are familiar with the socio-cultural context, language and communication habits. This means that they may have a better understanding of the situation of persons with the same social background.

However, in many contexts more than one marginalised group is directly or indirectly affected by an intervention. As it is not possible to involve representatives of all marginalised groups in the evaluation team, there is a risk of ignoring a particular group. One may decide to involve a representative from a marginalised group that is directly targeted by the intervention in the evaluation team, but particularly in contexts in which there are multiple forms of intersectional discrimination, the ability of all team members to empathetically understand the perspective of other marginalised groups is a key required skill. Higher levels of own personal involvement – particularly in situations marked by conflict – may not be conducive to this impartial empathetic stance.

Furthermore, finding representatives from marginalised groups that have substantial experience in evaluation methods is often a challenge. If they do not have prior experience in evaluation or research, they may need more training and coaching both before and during the evaluation, which has time and budget implications. Informal and formal hierarchies can also hinder younger or less experienced team members from expressing their needs and perspective in the team.

Gendered norms may also play a role and influence power dynamics in the team. Being aware of these dynamics is important to ensure the meaningful participation of rights-holders. Internal communication which is sensitive to gender dynamics and cultural differences helps ensure that all members have sufficient space to assert their position and voice their concerns.

Box 5 Participation of rights-holders in evaluation teams

In the evaluation of Oxfam’s multi-country programme on the health and education rights of children and young people, young people were involved as peer evaluators to better understand the local context and ensure communication with young people. The experience was positive but time-demanding, particularly for the senior international evaluators who coached the young team members (Van Esbroek et al., 2016).

In the evaluation of the BMZ Action Plan for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities, an experienced evaluator with a disability who served as a lead representative of a disabled people’s organisation was involved in one of the field studies as a national consultant, which had a very positive effect on the evaluation process (Schwedersky et al., 2017).

If the evaluability assessment shows that a full involvement of members of marginalised groups in the evaluation team is infeasible, other modes of participation opportunities should be explored. For example, at certain points of the evaluation different members of specific groups could be involved as facilitators of interviews or focus groups. Fairness is important to ensure that their participation is meaningful, which includes them receiving adequate remuneration for their work and their perspective being taken seriously by the other team members.

Avoiding harm to staff involved in research and evaluation is both an ethical and a human rights issue (see Chapter 2.2). Research has shown that safety concerns, difficult working conditions, role conflicts and hierarchical dependencies are current challenges faced by both national and international researchers conducting research and evaluation activities in the Global South (Kaplan et al., 2019; Kuhnt et al., 2025; Steinert et al., 2021).

Risks and related mitigation measures should therefore be considered beforehand when involving rights-holders and their representatives in evaluation teams. In particular, if an evaluation addresses politically or culturally sensitive issues, members of marginalised groups involved in evaluation teams might be exposed to the negative reactions of local communities or authorities. Ensuring their protection therefore is a challenge, even more so in a remote evaluation.

The third type – **representative participation** – implies inclusive and gender-balanced steering mechanisms of evaluations, such as reference groups (UNEG, 2024). Adequate representation of women in reference groups is now commonplace. In comparison, marginalised groups and their civil society representatives are still rarely involved in reference groups, even in evaluations that explicitly follow an HRBA (Worm et al., 2022). To ensure meaningful participation, representatives of rights-holders and marginalised groups should have a voice in the reference group or other steering mechanisms. Here again, the challenge is to decide which group(s) should be involved (see above).

Box 6 Participation of rights-holders in reference groups

- The reference group for the UN Women evaluation on the rights of women migrant workers was composed of six UN Women staff members and one representative of a civil society network (UN Women, 2017a: 74).
- International and German civil society organisations advocating for the rights of persons with disabilities as well as the monitoring desk for the CRPD at the German Institute for Human Rights were included in the reference group of the evaluation of the BMZ Action Plan for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities. In the field studies, members of disabled people’s organisations participated in kick-off and validation workshops (Schwedersky et al., 2017).

The fourth type – **transformative participation** – implies that rights-holders are involved on equal terms at all stages of the evaluation process. It is the most encompassing level of participation, by putting rights-holders at the centre of decision-making processes that affect their own economic, social, cultural and political situation and well-being.

Transformative participation is closely linked to the human rights principle of empowerment. Tracing back its origins to feminist theories from the Global South, empowerment is deeply rooted in the gender discourse in development. Empowerment is therefore not primarily framed in terms of a human rights perspective but rather stems from a social justice approach. In development cooperation, attempts have been made to bring the human rights and empowerment discourses together, with the main aim of giving marginalised people and groups a stronger voice (Batliwala, 2008; Calvès, 2009).

Empowerment generally refers to strengthening those groups and individuals who are most marginalised. In this sense, empowerment is supposed to contribute to the development of fairer power dynamics. In terms of content, a human rights-based evaluation aims at gaining knowledge about (1) what duty bearers did to promote empowerment and (2) how marginalised rights-holders empowered themselves in the context of a development intervention, such as whether – after an intervention – rights-holders gained more control over their lives and could exert more effective influence over discriminatory power dynamics. In terms of its process a human rights-based evaluation should (1) empower rights-holders to know and claim their rights and (2) ensure that rights-holders are able to use the evaluation to facilitate their struggle regarding the realisation of their rights.

In the following, we outline how participation and empowerment could be implemented at the different levels of the HRIIS.

At the **human rights-sensitive** level, it is important to include rights-holders in the evaluation process and provide a space where rights-holders can express their views freely. The act of voicing concerns and sharing information may have empowering potential while simultaneously providing the evaluation with insights from multiple perspectives. It can be most feasible to do so during data collection. To achieve this effect, evaluators should deploy data collection methods that aim to strengthen the agency of interviewees (e.g. through story-telling techniques) to support them in taking active roles in change processes.

At the **human rights-responsive** level, an evaluation provides multiple opportunities for different stakeholder groups - in particular rights-holders - to voice their views without evaluators giving up (partial) control of the process. In the context of strengthening empowerment and participation, compensation does not primarily refer to financial compensation but also includes information that can further rights-holders’ struggle for

recognition or fulfilment of their rights. Hence, evaluators should work towards a fair data collection and analysis process. Preparing the evaluation results in a way that is accessible and appropriate for participants is one example. Furthermore, debriefing workshops can enable marginalised rights-holders to receive aggregated information about their own data and, through their feedback, ensure that appropriate conclusions and recommendations are drawn from this information. This echoes empowerment evaluation, an approach that aims at fostering self-determination by providing people with the tools and knowledge they need to monitor and evaluate their own performance and accomplish their goals. This approach has primarily been applied to and recommended for the evaluation of community-based initiatives and projects. The aim of such evaluations is to empower people to initiate change or raise their voice for change (Fetterman and Wandersman, 2005; Wolfe et al., 2016: 51-52; Wandersman et al., 2016).

Empowerment and participation at the **human rights-transformative** level favours the co-creation of the evaluation together with rights-holders throughout the evaluation process. For example, rights-holders may already be involved in early stages of developing the evaluation design and may therefore co-determine the questions and methods of the evaluation. Likewise, recommendations may be co-created by evaluators and (representatives of) rights-holders.

3.4.2 Non-discrimination and equality of opportunities

The HRBA to development aims at overcoming de jure and de facto patterns of discrimination by addressing the underlying causes of inequalities and exclusion. Programming, monitoring and evaluating human rights-based development interventions therefore requires (1) identifying marginalised and vulnerable groups (in a vulnerability analysis) while also protecting them and (2) disaggregating data to be able to assess the specific impact of interventions on different marginalised groups or lives. By incorporating the non-discrimination principle in the evaluation methodology, evaluators also do justice to the “leave no behind” (LNOB) principle and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and assure, at the same time, that the principle of equal opportunities is integrated and respected.

Systematically incorporating non-discrimination and equality of opportunities as principles is both required by normative (e.g., fairness, ethics) and qualitative (e.g. sound methodology) aspects of evaluation standards. Assessing the effects of interventions on different groups, including marginalised groups, increases the accuracy and credibility of evaluations.⁸

The global indicator framework for the SDGs explicitly recommends disaggregating data: “Sustainable Development Goal indicators should be disaggregated, where relevant, by income, sex, age, race, ethnicity, migratory status, disability and geographic location, or other characteristics, in accordance with the Fundamental Principles of Official Statistics” (UN, 2022: 1).

Current evaluation guidance also recommends disaggregating indicators whenever possible and disaggregating data beyond the binary gender concept, as well as including other dimensions of exclusion and discrimination such as age, gender identity or sexual orientation (UNEG, 2024; OECD, 2023). Although data disaggregation along the binary gender concept and other factors such as age or income is now well-established, the analysis of multiple forms of discrimination and of intersectionality is a major challenge for evaluators (Worm et al., 2022; OECD, 2023). Despite these challenges, there are entry points to implement the principle of non-discrimination in the evaluation process.

Conducting a vulnerability analysis and disaggregating data are two key aspects of implementing the non-discrimination principle in the evaluation process. How comprehensively this is analysed depends on the human rights level chosen.

⁸ Both principles, non-discrimination and equality of opportunities, are so closely interlinked that the realisation of the one principle is almost synchronous with the realisation of the other principle. In this section, we focus on the principle of non-discrimination to achieve a better understanding and increased readability of the text. However, in our view the realisation of equality of opportunities is also covered and included at all times through the appropriate integration of non-discrimination.

At the **human rights-sensitive** level, implementing non-discrimination implies that evaluators conduct a basic vulnerability analysis based on existing data that includes an assessment of the human rights situation and key discrimination patterns in the intervention context. When designing the methodology, the evaluation team therefore reflects on the dimensions of discrimination that play a role in the specific context of the evaluated intervention.

This can be a part of the stakeholder assessment (see Chapter 3.3). The challenge is to identify the key dimensions that should be assessed in implementing the evaluation without overlooking a major dimension or overstress the evaluation. The evaluation team justifies which key dimensions were selected and why. In the implementation process, the evaluation team applies qualitative or quantitative methods that provide sufficient disaggregated data to assess whether and how an intervention has addressed the major marginalised groups and the key dimensions of discrimination. Likewise, the evaluation team considers the major patterns of gender-based discrimination without – at a human rights-sensitive level – necessarily analysing the structural causes of gender inequality in depth.

The evaluation of the BMZ Action Plan for the Inclusion of Persons with Disabilities underlines that due to the lack of disaggregated information on the number, living conditions and needs of persons with disabilities, they were often considered as a homogenous group (Schwedersky et al., 2017: 65) when, in fact, people with different physical or cognitive challenges required different interventions.

In many countries, evaluators face difficulties in finding appropriate data on gender diversity and the situation and needs of LGBTI+ persons. Data collection on these needs may – depending on the country in which the evaluation takes place – have to take extraordinary care to ensure no harm is being caused by revealing or allowing to infer a person's gender identity. In fact, this may make such data collection irresponsible in the context of an evaluation project. This dearth of information in turn makes it difficult to operationalise the concept of gender diversity (see Chapter 2) (see, e.g., Brüntrup-Seidemann et al., 2021).

At the **human rights-responsive** level non-discrimination implies a deeper vulnerability analysis, including an assessment of multiple forms of discrimination and intersectionality.

Instead of considering only the major patterns of inequality, in a human rights-responsive vulnerability analysis, evaluators identify the root causes, links and causal relationships between various grounds and dimensions of discrimination. Such intersectional discrimination could, for example, manifest itself between gender and social status or between disability and income. In many cases, programme documents and the monitoring systems of the evaluated interventions provide information about marginalised groups (e.g. poor women), but rarely on less evident intersectional links (for example between gender and ethnicity). If this is the case, academic studies and grey literature may help to collect additional information. Interviews with key resource persons at the beginning of an evaluation may also provide important information on intersectional links. Finally, carefully planned and conducted interviews or focus group discussions with members of marginalised groups (for example poor women or persons with disabilities) may give valuable information on intersectional issues. For example, in the evaluation of the UNFPA-UNICEF joint programme on the abandonment of female genital mutilation, women, men, teenagers, girls, and boys were involved in focus-group discussions. Specific attention was also given to other characteristics, such as marital status or geographic location (UNFPA, 2019b).

At the human rights-responsive level, evaluators apply appropriate qualitative or quantitative methods to collect or analyse disaggregated data and assess if and how interventions succeed in including marginalised groups and addressing intersecting forms of discrimination.

If sufficient data can be provided by the M&E systems of the evaluated interventions, the national statistical offices or existing surveys, an in-depth quantitative analysis is possible but often resource and time intensive. Box 7 shows how a UNICEF study assessed the cost-effectiveness of health and nutrition interventions by comparing interventions reaching poor and non-poor groups of children.

It is, however, not always feasible to assess all aspects of intersectionality. In our own evaluation on supporting gender equality in post-conflict contexts we therefore only examined critical overlaps in discrimination, e.g. between gender and ethnicity (Brüntrup-Seidemann et al., 2021). A vulnerability analysis conducted in the planning and design phase helps to establish a common understanding in the evaluation team on the critical links to be examined in the implementation phase.

Box 7 UNICEF study on cost-effectiveness of health and nutrition interventions

A UNICEF study on an equity-enhancing approach to child survival analysed the cost-effectiveness of health and nutrition interventions. One of the questions was “are investments that focus on reaching the poor with such interventions more cost-effective than investments in the non-poor?”

The study selected 51 countries either with relatively high rates of under-five mortality (at least 30 deaths per 1,000 live births) or substantial numbers of under-five deaths (at least 15,000 deaths annually), and sufficient data to track changes in intervention coverage over the period studied. The main data sources were household surveys carried out in accordance with international standards, including the Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS) and Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS).

Using survey data for each of the 51 countries, the study team then examined changes in coverage of six tracer indicators among poor and non-poor groups between the years 2003 and 2016. The cost-effectiveness analysis was carried out for a subset of 24 countries. Data on the costs of intervention coverage was drawn from existing peer-reviewed studies. The additional costs associated with reaching poorer children, who are often located in hard-to-reach areas, were calculated.

A key finding was that although the investment needed to improve coverage among the poor was greater than that required to reach the non-poor, the number of deaths averted per 1 million US dollars invested was around 1.8 times higher among the poor than among the non-poor. The study concludes that equity-enhancing approaches, although more costly, deliver a substantially greater return in terms of lives saved, compared to equivalent levels of investment among non-poor groups.

Source: UNICEF, 2017b.

A transformative evaluation aims at overcoming de jure or de facto discrimination by analysing and addressing its root causes in legislation, customs, norms and practices. Hence, the **human rights-transformative** level implies setting a strong focus in the methodology on assessing intersectionality and the underlying factors that lead to the discrimination of marginalised groups. A detailed assessment of power dynamics between genders and between groups of rights-holders is therefore part of the vulnerability analysis.

In the implementation process, a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods are applied to assess if and how the intervention has had an impact on these dynamics. Based on the findings, the evaluation proposes pathways of change to overcome de jure and de facto discrimination and achieve greater gender equality. Marginalised rights-holders use the findings and recommendations to highlight discriminatory norms and practices, claim their rights and actively bring about change.

3.4.3 Accountability and transparency

Accountability is both a core human rights principle (UNEG 2024) and one of the core functions of evaluation (Stockmann, 2022) – meaning that the human rights principle and the evaluation function converge. However, the human rights principle adds clarity in identifying who is accountable to whom.

Given that evaluations are often used in the context of a commissioning or funding body overseeing the work of an implementing partner or agency, accountability may sometimes be understood as being limited to holding the implementing partner accountable vis-à-vis the funder. A human rights perspective emphasises that there is also accountability of all duty-bearers engaged in and responsible for a development intervention (as primary or secondary duty-bearers) vis-à-vis the rights-holders participating in or targeted by the intervention (Winters, 2010). As such, a human rights perspective adds a complementary focus to accountability.

Major aspects of implementing the accountability principle in the evaluation process are identifying the duty-bearers and their respective obligations, choosing an adequate design to assess the implementation of these obligations and avoiding harm and unintended effects on human rights.

Implementing the accountability principle implies a dialogue between evaluators and (primary and secondary) duty-bearers about the extent to which they have complied with their human rights obligations and are accountable to the rights-holders. Depending on the context, this dialogue may be a challenge, particularly if the intervention evaluated does not put an explicit focus on human rights. Both development institutions and partner country officials may be reluctant to engage in a dialogue involving such human rights-informed aspects of accountability. Government partners may fear that they may be held responsible and potentially be shamed for human rights deficits in their countries. Officials from development cooperation institutions, programme managers and staff from development agencies implementing the intervention may express concern over the politicisation of development issues if human rights are explicitly addressed in the evaluation. How intensive and explicit this dialogue is, depends on the political context and on the purpose of the evaluation. Evaluators need adequate communication skills to address these sensitive issues with the evaluation stakeholders.

Being accountable to a variety of stakeholders involves being transparent about processes, agendas and results of an evaluation. Individuals should be able to understand and assess duty bearers' actions. To this end, such actions and their evaluations must be transparent, comprehensible and accountable (BMZ, 2023c). Transparency is therefore strongly intertwined with accountability. The principle of transparency should be upheld throughout all stages of the evaluation process. This is in line with accepted norms and standards of good evaluation practice, as transparency "establishes trust and builds confidence, enhances stakeholder ownership and increases public accountability" (UNEG, 2016: 12). However, evaluation practice seems to fall short of this ideal. Published evaluation reports do not usually provide many details on the evaluation process, the methodology applied and the information and dissemination procedures. Reports rarely describe how rights-holders were informed about the evaluation and if they had the opportunity to discuss the findings with the evaluators (Worm et al., 2022).

In terms of applying transparency and accountability at the **human rights-sensitive** level, evaluators should identify duty-bearers and their respective obligations in a stakeholder assessment (see Chapter 3.3). Based on this analysis, evaluators assess the extent to which development institutions and their partners have complied with their core obligations and implemented policies or strategies that foster the realisation of relevant rights in the context of the intervention.

Avoiding harm and unintended effects on human rights, in accordance with the due diligence and do-no-harm principles (see Chapter 2.4), relates both to the methodological approach and to the ethics of evaluators. Prior to the implementation phase, evaluators should reflect on possible negative effects of the intervention for rights-holders, in particular for marginalised groups. This reflection can be based on available safeguard analyses and programme documents of the intervention that they evaluate. If these analyses are not available, the identification of potential negative human rights effects can be part of a vulnerability analysis.

Evaluators should inform all relevant duty-bearers and rights-holders about the purpose of the evaluation and the evaluation process. Rights-holders consulted in the evaluation should be informed about the evaluation prior to interviewing them, which is also prescribed by the principle of voluntary and informed consent and professional ethical standards (see Chapter 2.2).

In the implementation process, evaluators assess the extent to which development institutions have monitored and eventually mitigated such effects. Additional information on unintended negative effects that were not foreseen or analysed in safeguard analyses can also be obtained during the implementation phase in interviews. If evaluators opt for a more thorough assessment of negative impacts on human rights, they may make use of and integrate human rights impact assessment (HRIA) tools in the evaluation process and methodology. HRIA are rooted in international human rights law and use human rights standards and principles as analytical criteria. The focus of these tools differs depending on the rights or sectors assessed. The methodology is similar and includes a step-by-step process from screening and identifying potential impacts on human rights, data collection, analysis of impacts, impact mitigation and management to conclusions and recommendations (World Bank and Nordic Trust Fund, 2013; Danish Institute for Human Rights, 2020).

Evaluation results should, in general, be accessible to the rights-holders of the intervention or their representatives. This may include easy-to-read formats or other ways of disseminating evaluation findings than reports, for example in comics or short films.

Box 8 Applying human rights impact assessment tools in evaluations

In response to allegations by the media on human rights abuses in the context of conservation work undertaken by the World Wildlife Fund for Nature (WWF) in four African countries, WWF Germany commissioned an independent evaluation to examine its human rights due diligence processes. The evaluation assessed to what extent WWF Germany has a procedure in place to identify, prevent and mitigate adverse impacts of WWF's activities on human rights. The evaluation refers to core international human rights instruments as well as to the labour standards of the ILO. The evaluation was guided by the United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights and partly applied a HRIA tool.

Source: Szeponik et al., 2019

The do-no-harm principle is also related to the accountability of the evaluation team towards the rights-holders involved in the evaluation process. It includes ethical conduct by evaluators and fairness towards the rights-holders involved in the evaluation (see Chapter 4).

At the **human rights-responsive** level, evaluators systematically integrate an assessment of the extent to which an intervention has supported duty-bearers in realising human rights into the evaluation process.

Evaluators first identify the relevant primary and secondary duty-bearers and their corresponding obligations in the stakeholder assessment. Evaluators then integrate the principle of progressive realisation (i.e. assessing the extent to which duty-bearers have taken steps with a view to progressively achieve the full realisation of human rights, see Chapter 3.2) into the design of the evaluation.

This may imply, for example, operationalising elements of the AAAQ framework in the evaluation questions or in the theory of change. Evaluators may also assess the extent to which the indicators of an intervention reflect the AAAQ criteria and eventually adapt them for the evaluation.

Integrating transparency at this level, obliges evaluators to involve rights-holders or their representatives in the validation and discussion of the evaluation findings. One challenge is that civil society organisations often depend on and compete for donor support. It is often difficult to find self-representation or grassroots organisations that genuinely represent the views and interests of rights-holders and marginalised groups. One feasible option is to conduct short de-briefing and validation workshops at the community level to discuss preliminary findings with the rights-holders that participated in interviews or focus group discussions.

Box 9 Operationalising the principle of progressive realisation by applying the AAAQ criteria

Flores Baquero et al. (2016) have operationalised the principle of progressive realisation, and applied the AAAQ criteria in their case study on a water project in a rural municipality in northern Nicaragua. The study design was case control-based, with a stratified sample splitting households served by providers and self-provided households.

Household surveys included a set of questions and indicators that covered the first four dimensions of the right to water (availability, physical accessibility, affordability, acceptability). The fifth dimension (quality) was measured using a technical audit of the water quality at different points. Indicators were also set for all five dimensions. Such an approach is feasible for monitoring and evaluating the progressive realisation of the right to water at a local level. However, it implies higher costs than traditional approaches.

Source: Flores Baquero et al., 2016

Accountability in a human rights perspective means framing conclusions and recommendations in a way that shows the degree to which duty-bearers have made progress towards the full provision or realisation of rights and the degree to which this has not been the case. The dissemination strategy and the formats chosen for the dissemination should therefore not only be targeted at duty-bearers but also at rights-holders or their representatives. This kind of dissemination strategy opens room for dialogue between duty-bearers and rights-holders, for example civil society and advocacy organisations, on the progress achieved as well as on missed opportunities or insufficient progress towards the full realisation of human rights.

Accountability at the **human rights-transformative** level, means that evaluations aim at empowering rights-holders to claim their rights. Therefore, advocacy or human rights organisations are often substantially involved. Evaluators set a focus on evaluation designs that explicitly refer to the human rights protection system and respective redress mechanisms. Therefore, the evaluation process strengthens human rights accountability mechanisms, either in the donor or the partner country. In terms of transparency, evaluators actively involve rights-holders and their representatives in informing their communities of the purpose and the results of the evaluation. Sharing the evaluation findings in a transparent way requires conducting a dialogue with the rights-holders and the wider community on how the evaluation has addressed power dynamics and how they can use these findings to bring about change.

Box 10 Evaluations and the right to remedies and redress

In 2011, the UN Environment Programme (UNEP) released a report documenting the large-scale contamination of the water and soil caused by the oil industry in Ogoniland, Nigeria, and made recommendations for clean-up and immediate support for the affected communities. In 2020, Amnesty International as well as Nigerian and Dutch NGOs examined the extent to which Nigeria's government and the Anglo-Dutch company Shell had implemented UNEP's recommendations and complied with their human rights obligations. The evaluation referred to international human rights treaties and the Nigerian constitution, which guarantee the right to an adequate standard of living, water, health, an effective remedy, freedom of expression and access to information.

Regarding the corporate accountability of Shell, the evaluation was guided by the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (AI, 2020). The evaluation findings showed that efforts made by the Nigerian government and Shell to implement the recommendations of the 2011 report were far too weak to ensure an effective clean-up and support for the communities that had been affected. Among other measures, the evaluation recommended adequate compensation of affected communities for their losses and that Shell improve its maintenance of pipelines to prevent oil spills.

In 2021, the Court of Appeal in The Hague ruled in favour of four Nigerian farmers who had sued Shell in 2008 together with the Dutch NGOs involved in the above-mentioned evaluation. The court ruled that Shell had violated its duty of care and should pay compensation to the farmers. In December 2022, Shell agreed to pay 15 million euros in compensation to the affected communities.

Sources: AI, 2020; Business and Human Rights Resource Center, 2025; Kirchner, 2021

Access to remedies is not an automatic consequence of standard development cooperation evaluations. Although evaluators may recommend various mechanisms to improve the access of rights-holders to complaint and redress mechanisms, it is difficult to follow-up such recommendations in the current institutional setting of development cooperation.

Evaluations and their follow-up do not replace independent complaint mechanisms (Kämpf, 2013). Therefore, the transformative level of accountability is hard to achieve in standard development cooperation evaluations. If evaluators strive towards this, they need a dissemination strategy that is also targeted at actors of the human rights protection system as well as human rights advocacy organisations.

3.5 How are human rights principles and professional evaluation standards linked?

One argument often put forward in discussions on human rights-based evaluations is that they are not compatible with professional evaluation standards, particularly regarding the independence of evaluators vis-à-vis different stakeholder groups. A concise comparison of human rights principles and selected evaluation standards shows that they do not contradict each other across all levels of the HRIIS. However, there are indeed some tensions between evaluation standards and the transformative level of applying human rights principles to the evaluation process. This mainly concerns issues of independence and impartiality. In the following we outline consequences for selected human rights principles.

Participation

Evaluation standards on participation require the consultation and involvement of various (groups of) key stakeholders in the evaluation process. Evaluations should follow a partnership approach, thus realising an “inclusive process, involving different stakeholders such as government, parliament, civil society, intended beneficiaries and international partners” (OECD DAC, 2010: 7).

Stakeholders should be given the opportunity to convey their views on the evaluation design, participate in interviews during the implementation and comment on the draft report (Quality Standards 2.5, 3.3, and 3.15; OECD, 2010). Evaluation standards do not specify or prescribe which stakeholders should be involved in the steering mechanisms of evaluations, such as reference groups. The human rights-responsive level of implementing participation explicitly requires the involvement of representatives of rights-holders and marginalised groups in the steering mechanisms of the evaluation without compromising their independence or impartiality. Both the human rights-sensitive and the responsive level of participation are therefore compatible with the evaluation standards.

The human rights-transformative level of participation implies that rights-holders have substantial control over the evaluation process. Such an understanding may create tensions with the evaluation standard of independence, according to which “evaluators are independent from the development intervention, including its policy, operations and management functions, as well as intended beneficiaries” (Quality Standard 3.2; OECD, 2010: 11). Similarly, the UNEG Norms and Standards state that “independence entails the ability to evaluate without undue influence by any party” (UNEG, 2016: 11).

Thus, when implementing participation at the human rights-transformative level, there is a tension between the evaluators relinquishing some of their decision-making power to rights-holders and the standards of independence and impartiality. Such tensions between evaluation standards are commonplace. For example, the timeliness of an evaluation may be at odds with reaching satisfactory levels of validity of the findings and conclusions. Although neither the OECD DAC nor the UNEG standards explicitly deal with such tensions, they allow for some level of context-dependent or incomplete implementation of the standards. At this stage, there is no blueprint of how to resolve the tension between participation and independence/impartiality at the transformative level. In practice, a transformative approach has mainly been implemented in smaller evaluations of projects managed by civil society organisations who put particular emphasis on the ownership of rights-holders. In contrast, it is not considered appropriate for strategic or programme evaluations by some agencies (BMZ, 2021).

Non-discrimination

The OECD DAC Quality Standard 2.9 on the selection of the evaluation approach and the methodology explicitly mentions that “disaggregated data should be presented to clarify any differences between sexes and between different groups of poor people, including excluded groups” (OECD, 2010: 10). Therefore, it is fully compatible with the human rights-sensitive and responsive level of implementing non-discrimination.

The transformative level implies an in-depth analysis of multiple forms of discrimination and intersectionality, and as such does not contradict evaluation standards, even if – in practice – it may pose methodological challenges to evaluators. The importance of data disaggregation and intersectionality analysis are also reflected in the definition of the revised OECD DAC criteria (OECD, 2019) and the respective guidance documents on how to apply the criteria (OECD, 2021 and 2023).

Accountability

The OECD DAC quality standards for development evaluation define accountability as “*mutual accountability for results*” (Quality Standard 1.4; OECD, 2010: 7). Accountability thus implies a partnership dialogue between development partners and partner countries on the results they have achieved, as well as how and why results could or could not be achieved. Evaluations may also have the purpose of accounting for public expenditures to taxpayers and include decisions on continuing or discontinuing projects or programmes (Quality Standard 2.1; OECD, 2010: 8). Accountability includes the systematic response and follow-up to evaluation recommendations (Quality Standard 4.2; OECD, 2010: 15).

The human rights definition goes beyond the concept of “mutual accountability” for development results by assessing the extent to which development cooperation institutions and their partners have complied with their obligations to respect, protect and fulfil human rights. The human rights understanding adds a new dimension to the concept of accountability – that between rights-holders and duty-bearers.

Accountability, as defined in the OECD DAC quality standards, is fully compatible with the human rights-sensitive and responsive level in human rights-based evaluations. Including the notion of progressive realisation of human rights is possible in a dialogue on mutual accountability and the achievements and results of a development intervention.

Likewise, assessing the unintended negative impacts of development interventions on human rights has now become part of many safeguarding policies and appraisal guidelines of multilateral and bilateral development agencies (e.g., UNDP, 2014, World Bank, 2017, BMZ, 2013). The OECD guidance on applying a human rights and gender equality lens to the OECD evaluation criteria emphasises the importance of analysing unintended negative effects on human rights and gender equality, particularly on marginalised population groups (OECD, 2023).

According to the evaluation guidelines of the BMZ, evaluations should examine unintended negative impacts on human rights and compliance with human rights due diligence in the planning and implementation of development interventions (BMZ, 2021: 10).

Evaluation ethics and ethical codes of conduct also require evaluators to respect human rights, and are mindful of gender, age, sexual orientation and other factors which might cause harm (see, for example, OECD DAC Quality Standard 1.3 on evaluation ethics; OECD DAC, 2010: 6).

The transformative level implies that evaluations contribute to facilitating the access of rights-holders to complaint and redress mechanisms. This goes beyond, but does not contradict, the OECD DAC evaluation standards on the use and follow-up of evaluation findings (see Quality Standards 4.1 to 4.3; OECD, 2010: 15). However, to enable such a use, evaluation findings and recommendations need to be disseminated to a wide range of stakeholders, including civil society and human rights organisations. Again, this does not contradict current evaluation standards, but may require additional investment in time and financial resources that will have to be balanced with other requirements of the standards.

Transparency

Evaluation standards primarily link transparency to the dissemination and publication of evaluation results (OECD, 2010; BMZ, 2021). The human rights-based understanding emphasises the importance of informing rights-holders throughout the evaluation process and involving them in the validation of findings.

According to the OECD DAC quality standards, evaluation results should be “presented in an accessible format systematically distributed internally and externally for learning and follow-up actions and to ensure transparency” (Quality Standard 4.3; OECD, 2010: 16).

This is fully compatible with the human rights-sensitive level, which requires rights-holders and their representatives to have easy access to the findings and recommendations of the evaluation. It does not contradict the human rights-responsive level and the involvement of rights-holders in the validation of findings.

There is a tension with the transformative level, which implies a strong involvement of rights-holders in informing their communities of the evaluation and sharing the results of it. Depending on the degree to which rights-holders control the evaluation process, it could come into conflict with the standard of independence (see also the transformative level of participation discussed above).

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

International human rights law clearly states that development cooperation should not have a negative impact on human rights. Furthermore, it should contribute to enhancing the capacity of governments and other partners of development cooperation institutions (i.e. duty-bearers) to comply with their human rights obligations and responsibilities.

Several donors' policies and strategies call for mainstreaming an HRBA to development by systematically integrating human rights principles in development cooperation, including monitoring and evaluation. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development and the SDG framework explicitly incorporate human rights and gender equality. Therefore, the key issue is not whether the evaluation of development cooperation should integrate human rights standards and principles but how they should be applied in practice.

Our view is that core human rights and gender equality norms and principles should guide all evaluations. However, the intensity to which these are applied to the evaluation process may vary. We have shown flexible ways of implementing human rights principles in the evaluation process by using a scale that differentiates between three levels of intensity (sensitive, responsive, transformative).

Figure 6 shows selected human rights principles and summarises the key elements of a human rights-based evaluation process according to the three levels and the respective human rights principles.

This differentiated view of how human rights principles may inform the evaluation process is intended to facilitate conceptualising human rights as a key quality dimension of all evaluations. By providing a more nuanced language to describe the level of implementing a human rights-based approach for different human rights principles, it moves the focus from labelling evaluation approaches and methods as "human rights-based" (or not) to identifying the potential, strengths and limitations of evaluations with regard to incorporating human rights principles in the evaluation process.

Professional evaluation standards and the requirements for human rights-sensitive evaluations are largely compatible and mutually reinforcing. Therefore, good standard evaluation practice is and should be human rights-based, at least at the human rights-sensitive level. In many strategic evaluations of development interventions, it is also possible to apply human rights principles at the responsive level.

However, depending on the purpose, context and available resources for the evaluation, it may not be possible or appropriate to apply all principles beyond the sensitive level. Evaluators may, for example, face practical challenges in finding adequate modes of meaningful participation for marginalised groups. In many strategic evaluations, participation is mainly ensured by representatives of civil society organisations and not by the direct involvement of rights-holders at the community level.

Furthermore, applying participation at the transformative level may lead to tensions with the professional evaluation standard that guarantees the independence of evaluators from the evaluation stakeholders (see Chapter 3.5). Depending on the characteristics of the evaluation – including its object, purpose and resources – it may therefore make sense to first ensure that the level of human rights sensitivity is reached for all human rights principles, and secondly that resources are applied thoughtfully to apply responsive or transformative standards for a selected number of principles.

Based on the scale and framework we propose, evaluators could define in the evaluability assessment the extent to which each principle can be applied in the evaluation process. This would contribute to clarifying the ambition and practice of human rights in evaluation and thereby fostering transparency and constructive criticism of relevant process characteristics. We believe that discussing human rights in evaluation in such a differentiated manner will ultimately strengthen the reflexion of the human rights dimension of evaluations and contribute to the progressive implementation of human rights in evaluations.

Figure 6 Progressively implementing human rights principles in evaluations

Participation & Empowerment

Nominal or instrumental participation: Consultation of rights-holders or their representatives; ethical principles and code of conduct (voluntary informed consent; fairness in communication between evaluators and consulted rights-holders).

Instrumental or representative participation: Active involvement of rights-holders in the implementation phase, e.g. as facilitators, interviewers or team members.
Involvement of representatives of rights-holders in the steering mechanisms of the evaluation, e.g., reference groups.

Active involvement of rights-holders in all stages of the evaluation process: Decision on design, control over and active role in implementation; use of findings to initiate change, claim and realise rights.

Non-discrimination & Equality of Opportunity

Basic vulnerability analysis in the design phase: Including identification of the key dimensions of discrimination and major marginalised groups of rights-holders; in the implementation phase, analysis of available data or collection of disaggregated data that provides sufficient information to assess if and how the intervention has addressed these dimensions as well as marginalised groups.

Vulnerability analysis: Identification of the major causes, intersectional links and causal relationships between various grounds and dimensions of discrimination.
Disaggregation of data: Analysis or collection of disaggregated data that provides information on the extent to which the intervention has addressed intersecting forms of discrimination and succeeded in reaching and including marginalised groups.

Vulnerability analysis: Including a comprehensive assessment of intersectionality and of the underlying factors that lead to the discrimination of marginalised groups. Focus on power dynamics between genders and between groups of rights-holders and duty-bearers.
Disaggregation of data: Analysis and/or collection of disaggregated data that provides information on how the information has had an impact on these dynamics and contributed to overcoming discrimination and bringing about change.

Accountability & Transparency

Identification of duty-bearers and their core obligations in the stakeholder assessment; assessment of the extent to which duty-bearers have complied with these obligations.
Do-no-harm principle and non-intended effects: Identification of potential non-intended effects (in vulnerability analysis); and in the implementation assessment of the extent to which development institutions have monitored and/or mitigated unintended negative effects. Ethical code of conduct of the evaluators.

Identification of primary and secondary duty-bearers and their corresponding obligations in the stakeholder assessment; incorporating principle of progressive realisation in the design of the evaluation.
Choice of dissemination strategy and formats that is targeted at duty-bearers and rights-holders or their representatives, opens the room for dialogue on progress as well as missed opportunities for the realisation of human rights.

Focus on evaluation designs that explicitly refer to the human rights protection system and respective redress mechanisms.
Choice of dissemination strategy that is also targeted at actors of the human rights protection system and human rights advocacy organisations.

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